

Discovering, Identifying and Gauging (DIGging) epistemic properties of research processes and fields

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Epistemic properties of research processes and research fields play a crucial role in comparative science studies. However, they are rarely defined, and no protocols for their empirical identification exist. In this paper, we compare five methods—participant observation, interviews, document analysis, surveys, and bibliometrics—for their potential to discover, identify and gauge epistemic properties. The discussion relies on our own experiences with comparative empirical research and on the literature.

1. Introduction

Epistemic properties, which we define as properties of objects and methods of knowledge production that can generate affordances and constraints for knowledge-producing actions, play a crucial role in comparative science studies. They derive from and represent the influence on researchers' actions of physical characteristics of material objects and structural properties of knowledge. Examples include the degree of codification of knowledge (Zuckerman and Merton 1972: 303), which may affect the time it takes researchers to change their topics, the technical uncertainty of research processes (Whitley, 2000 [1984], pp. 119-123; Laudel & Gläser, 2014), which may affect the match between research projects and funding opportunities, or the interdisciplinarity (epistemic diversity) of fields or research processes, which may affect the match between a field's research practices and expectations built into evaluations (Rafols et al., 2012).¹

Despite their importance for comparative science studies, epistemic properties (EPs) of research are rarely defined, and no protocols for their empirical identification exist. This is not surprising given the lack of theoretical support and methodological guidance. EPs derive from physical properties of objects and logical properties of knowledge, neither of which are subject to sociological theories. It is therefore impossible to derive from a theory which EPs might be relevant for a particular comparative research question, and no measurement scales exist. Relevant EPs must be *discovered* in empirical research. If the existence and relevance of some EP has been established by previous studies, instances of this property must be empirically *identified*. Finally, EPs must be *gauged*, and comparative scales must be created.

A further methodological challenge for DIGging (discovering, identifying, and gauging) EPs arises from their heterogeneity. EPs of research can be micro-level properties of individual research processes, aggregates of individual-level properties that describe a field, or holistic

¹ At the end of this paper there is a link to the list of epistemic properties we have identified so far, including indicators how to identify them as well as empirical examples.

field-level variables that exist only at the meso-level of fields. Specific empirical methods may be necessary to DIG particular EPs at specific levels of aggregation.

The aim of this paper is to review main methods of science studies regarding their capacity for DIGging EPs. The discussion relies on our own experiences with comparative empirical research and on the literature, which we can reference only very selectively due to space restrictions.

2. A review of methods for empirically DIGging epistemic properties

Table 1 provides an overview of the performance of the five main methodological approaches available to science studies. We will introduce each of them and provide examples of how they can be used for DIGging EPs.

Table 1: Characteristics of methodological approaches in science studies

<i>Method</i>	<i>Unique contribution</i>	<i>Limits</i>
Participant observation	Best approach to acquiring interactional expertise Data collection on research practices independently of the observed researchers' interpretation of their situation Most comprehensive data collection on research practices	Access to sites for observations is often difficult Narrow scope Unstructured idiosyncratic data Time consuming No access to unexplicated background knowledge that informs decisions of researchers
Interview	Access to knowledge and frames of researchers that shape their actions Probing questions enable an understanding of researchers' actions	Time-consuming acquisition of interactional expertise Data collection dependent on circumscribed interview situation Unstructured idiosyncratic data
Document analysis	Access to written communications researchers address to each other	Limited accessibility of some types of documents Stylized presentations of research Documents build on shared background knowledge that is not explicated
Survey	By design comparative Wide scope	Empirical phenomena of interest and ways in which they are described by researchers must be known ex ante Same questions must be applicable to all situations
Bibliometrics	Access to field-level properties	Field-delineation is problematic Dependence on data and source coverage

Participant observation is the utilisation of a lengthy co-presence with researchers to collect data on their everyday work practices. It has been introduced to science studies by laboratory studies (e.g. Latour & Woolgar, 1986 [1979]; Knorr-Cetina, 1981) and has since been used to create thick descriptions of research practices. EPs of these practices can be derived from these

descriptions. Longer stays with researchers support the acquisition of interactional expertise that is required to understand research practices (Collins, 2017, p. 314). Because of its comprehensive data collection and openness to unanticipated information, the approach is well suited to the discovery of new EPs. A main advantage of participant observation is that the collection of data about research practices does not depend on the observed researchers' interpretation of their situation. Major disadvantages arise from the fact that one or few sites must be observed for a longer time, and from the fact that data are unstructured and idiosyncratic, which means that their comparability can only be achieved in the subsequent data analysis. Furthermore, gaining access to sites for observations is often difficult due to the intrusive character of observations.

EPs can be identified by observations because researchers respond in their practices to material and logical properties of their research and talk about these properties in their scientific discussions, as in the following examples:

O1: At a poster session of a plant biology conference, a PhD student lamented that he has tried for almost two years to find an altered phenotype but didn't succeed. Discussants at the poster asked him, whether he had tried out certain stress conditions as well as other conditions in order to trigger an altered phenotype. However, it turned out that he had already tried out all these experimental alterations.

O2: A senior researcher at a plant biology conference commented on the production of phenotypes during his lecture: "Not having a phenotype is a problem, we got a bit stuck here".

The two observations reveal the high epistemic uncertainty (the uncertainty concerning the successful production of new knowledge) of particular research processes in plant biology. The only way of producing an altered phenotype of a plant, which is a main research object in plant biology, is a trial-and-error process of creating mutants and screening them for altered phenotypes. If this process does not lead to a scientifically interesting, altered phenotype, the researcher has no research object and has no choice but to repeat the creation of mutants under different experimental conditions.

Interviews are artificially created situations in which the interviewer (asking questions) and an interviewee (answering questions) jointly produce data. Interviews are probably the most widespread method in qualitative social science and are differentiated into many different forms (Flick, 2009). For our purposes semi-structured interviews are the most relevant form. The semi-structured interview is based on a list of questions that cover pre-established topics of interest but provides the opportunity to change the order of questions and their phrasing, to omit questions if the interviewee already provided the relevant information and to add questions to follow up on matters arising during the interview. This makes it possible to discover EPs through interviews. However, the time that is available to collect data with an interview (usually one to two hours per interviewee) and necessary to acquire interactional expertise for each interview limits the depth and scope of data collection through interview-based studies. The data collected through interviews are unstructured and idiosyncratic and must be rendered comparable in the subsequent data analysis.

EPs can be DIGged by analysing interviewees' descriptions of their research practices. The following two quotes exemplify the discovery of "Eigentime", a property that stands for "the dynamics of research objects and methods such as the speed of growth of biological systems or the frequency of occurrences of phenomena" (Gläser & Laudel, 2015, pp. 303-304):

I1: [In comparison to satellite images] one drone scene has about three centimetres resolution per pixel. And that means you have a very different amount of pixels when you investigate an area. And then it takes 10-12 hours to calculate such a scene. (Geography)

I2: Timing is very important for brain tumours. We look closely at the embryonal days during mouse pregnancy and induce changes at specific times. And this often does not work because sometimes pregnancies fail, sometimes they don't get pregnant and that is why it takes a relatively long time to do a successful experiment. (Oncology)

Those examples show very different research practices, in I1 we have a description of analysing visual survey data and in I2 of experiments with tumours in mouse embryos. These practices are hardly comparable on first glance but they share EPs, in this case Eigentime. In both cases the time it takes to conduct the empirical analysis is determined by a combination of properties of objects and methods. While the Eigentime of methods may change over time (for instance by using faster computers in the first case), material properties of objects often set hard limits (it is difficult to induce faster embryonal growth in mice). The example also demonstrates how the Eigentime of research processes may be comparatively gauged (being longer in I2).

Document analysis scrutinises the content of written communications produced in a field under study for information, which can be analysed quantitatively or qualitatively. This method is non-intrusive because it is applied to documents members of the field create for each other. This avoids the 'contamination' of data sources that occurs when researchers create accounts of their practices for outsiders. Getting access to some documents may be difficult, e.g. if they are confidential. Disadvantages arise from the analyst's lack of control of data production. For example, the analysis of publications, grant proposals or reviews of manuscripts must cope with highly stylised descriptions of research practices, which build on a shared understanding of research that remains implicit.

While the highly stylised descriptions of research practices in publications and grant proposals make the collection of data on research practices difficult, we can collect data about certain EPs. For example, the standardisation of fields' languages, which we understand as one part of the degree of codification of knowledge (Zuckerman & Merton, 1972, p. 303), can be gauged from project descriptions in grant proposals by analysing the prevalence of unambiguous technical terms. In the following example we underlined phrases that represent agreed-upon meanings. The frequency of such phrases can be used to estimate the standardisation of language in the field:

D1: With its C-terminal domain (CTD), Su(H) binds the just 16 amino acids spanning NT-box of H. In H-NT we identified a single amino acid essential for Su(H) binding. The affinity of H for Su(H) binding matches that of ICN. (Biology)

The underlined words and phrases are likely to carry unambiguous agreed-upon meanings that are different from the diffuse meanings of everyday language. Finding other documents from the field using the same terms in the same way can be used for corroboration. In the second example, we underlined terms that may or may be not technical terms but in any case are unlikely to represent agreed-upon meanings.

D2: In this way and by detailed indices, sources will be made accessible for further research on such topics as the development of the celebratory and symbolic character of Christian cult practices and the theological or rather ideological content of the texts directed to the venerated divinity in the ecclesiastical community throughout the centuries. (History)

In the second example it is difficult to find technical terms as in the other. While some of the underlined words and phrases may have agreed-upon meanings, this is not clear because definitions are rarely provided, and several definitions coexist for concepts like ideology. It can be shown that concepts like “Christian cult practices” or “ecclesiastical community” have context-specific meanings rather than field-specific agreed-upon meanings.

We can compare the standardisation of language in one field to that in another field on an ordinal scale of measure by stating “the knowledge in the field of D2 is less codified than that of D1”. This applies to most EPs because there are no basic reference quantities for their measurement.

Surveys ask a large group of respondents (who are a sample of a larger population) standardised questions about a pre-determined set of issues and collect standardised responses. The large number of respondents and the standardised answers enable statistical analyses of responses and conclusions about the population represented by the sample (Groves et al., 2004). Owing to its wide scope (its applicability to large numbers of researchers from all fields simultaneously), the survey is in the unique position to identify and gauge EPs. The method is comparative because the same questions and response options are applied to all respondents. This standardisation also creates major limitations of surveys. First, surveys can only ask about what is already known or at least hypothesized, i.e. they are not open to unanticipated information about new EPs. Second, it is very difficult to operationalize the identification and gauging of EPs across fields with their often strongly varying research practices.

We have not ourselves used surveys for DIGging EPs. Survey-based research that has been published so far does not appear to include specific questions about research practices or EPs, probably because it is not clear yet how the following two challenges can be overcome. First, the difference between analysts’ and researchers’ understanding of research practices and their properties must be bridged (Gläser, 2018, p. 1367). Second, since we cannot know in advance which properties are important and how they are expressed in responses in different fields, it is difficult to ask about them with standardised closed questions. Some ongoing work addresses these challenges (Velden & Tcypina, 2023). Overcoming them could make surveys an integral part of field-comparative science studies.

Bibliometrics is a collection of methods for the reconstruction of properties of research from bibliographic metadata and increasingly also the full texts of publications. Publications and their metadata are produced by researchers without interference by analysts, i.e. bibliometric methods are unobtrusive. They potentially provide unique access to EPs that only exist on the field level such as the epistemic diversity of fields. However, this requires a precise delineation of fields, which is a problem that bibliometrics has struggled with for a long time (Gläser et al., 2017). Furthermore, bibliometric methods depend on publication databases that store publication metadata. The application of bibliometric methods requires a thorough consideration of which publications and which of their metadata are (not) included in the database. Finally, it is not sufficiently clear yet how EPs are represented in bibliometric metadata or how bibliometric indicators are related to the theoretical concepts we want to operationalise.

A field-level property that may be measurable with bibliometric methods is a field's epistemic diversity, i.e. "the diversity of published knowledge claims about scientific problems, solutions, empirical objects, approaches and methods" (Gläser et al., 2015, p. 1007). This EP has gained prominence under the label "interdisciplinarity" (Rafols et al., 2012). All attempts to measure the epistemic diversity of fields depend on the prior delineation of the field or at least some set of papers that can be expected to 'contain' the topics in question (see Gläser et al., 2015).

It may also be possible to not only gauge but measure the previously discussed the standardisation of language (which we understand as part of the degree of codification of knowledge in a field). Linguistic approaches of measuring lexical diversity (McCarthy & Jarvis, 2010) and the application of large language models for the operationalisation of meaning as word-embedding vectors (Simons, Zichert & Wüthrich, 2023) look like promising approaches to measurement.

3. Conclusions

EPs of research processes and fields are a promising conceptual device for the comparison of research practices and fields because they can be defined at a level of abstraction between idiosyncratic research processes and binary distinctions between "hard" or "soft" sciences (Storer, 1967) or "urban" and "rural" fields (Becher & Trowler, 2001 [1989]). They can act as a theoretical anchor to not drown in a sea of descriptive case studies and at the same time provide the possibility to integrate different methods at a conceptual level. This is why their empirical investigation deserves more attention. Each of the five methodological approaches discussed in our paper supports a specific empirical contribution to this task. This is why combinations of these methods appear to be the most promising approach. Starting from concepts rather than operationalisations supports the combination of methods.

One intriguing corollary of the missing forced absence of epistemic properties from sociological theories is that the only way to progress in DIGging epistemic properties is a strong Grounded Theory approach. Over the last two decades, we have accumulated empirical findings on EPs, indicators of their presence, methods do DIG them and their role in explanations of differences between research processes and fields. We are currently consolidating our findings and created a database of epistemic properties, ways of DIGging them, and examples of their explanatory roles. We make this database publicly available to science studies as a community resource in the hope that the science studies community will utilise and contribute to our evolving grounded theory of how EPs affect processes in science: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1oZjsXXRQ-K7j6dQEcRSjOhYa-7U2mtC6sAGmg27FU0A>

Figure 1: QR-code for the database of epistemic properties

Open science practices

This paper does not systematically use empirical data.

We have created a living database of epistemic properties, which includes methodological recommendations, definitions, and examples. We make this database publicly available to science studies as a community resource: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1oZjsSXRQ-K7j6dQEcRSjOhYa-7U2mtC6sAGmg27FU0A>

Author contributions

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Competing interests

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